

THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSVERSAL COMPETENCIES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of developing transversal competencies of students in higher education institutions. The components and methods of transversal competencies aimed at the formation of students' citizenship in accordance with the education system corresponding to the developing society are analyzed. A set of transversal competencies is at the center of attention of the entire world education system and is recognized as necessary for the development of critical and innovative thinking, creative thinking, digital literacy, information literacy, problem solving, teamwork, foreign language proficiency, etc.*

Keywords: *transversal skills, transversal competence, skills of the XXI century, digital literacy, labor market.*

Introduction

The rapid development of society introduces new requirements to the education system. Students should not only receive the information provided, but also assimilate, process, develop and apply knowledge in accordance with the environment.

In the future, the existence of a nation will be judged not by its natural resources, but by the competitiveness of its people. Therefore, nowadays everyone should have the skills of the XXI century. For example, factors such as computer literacy, knowledge of foreign languages, cultural openness are prerequisites for personal development. Therefore, such programs as "digital Uzbekistan", "innovative education", "cultural and interreligious harmony" are one of the propaganda programs aimed at preparing our nation and people for the requirements of the XXI century.

The Head of our state in each of his speeches emphasizes the need to improve modern science and high technologies, invests all his strength and capabilities in this. The education system provides for the introduction of innovative educational technologies that meet the new principles of society - mobility, creativity, communication and communication. In education, the main attention should be paid to the development of creativity, critical thinking, and the ability to work in a team.

In the learning process, these competencies are widely used in the scientific literature under the names: general competencies (generic competencies), strategic competencies (Strategic competencies) and Core competencies (Core competencies).

Transversal competencies are characterized by the ability to adapt quickly and move from one field of activity to another, and also play a key role in achieving success in the labor market.

Today, the main goal of the university is not only to provide society with specialists, but also to meet all the needs of society, the use of digital technologies, creating flexibility and creativity in the labor market, training specialists with intercultural knowledge who are able to solve teamwork and independent decision-making through civic and professional skills.

Literature review

One of the main requirements of a developing society is communication and tolerance among students. In recent years, these structures have been viewed as components of transversal competence.

The concept of "transversal competence" appeared in Europe in the early 1970s. This concept was first proposed in 1972 in E. Faure's report "Learning to be: The World of Education Today and Tomorrow".

The author proposed two main ideologies: "continuing education" and "society of students" [1].

Transversal competencies as defined by UNESCO: critical and innovative thinking, interpersonal communication, global citizenship, physical and psychological health. The links between interdisciplinary competence and transversal competence have not yet been fully elucidated [2].

Traditional competencies are the ability to understand and apply knowledge such as calculus, logic, and literacy. However, transversal/non-cognitive skills include social, emotional competencies that enhance human interaction with society.[3]

Claudiu Langa, transversal competence ".. skills that go beyond a certain area and strengthen professional competence," he says [4].

Hollis Ashbaugh, Carla M. Johnston (2000), De Lange, P., Jackling, B. Gat (2006), transversal competencies are a set of skills necessary for professionals to complement professional competencies and achieve success in a particular field. [5].

The main part

Although the terminology and classification of transversal skills differ, as studies show, they primarily affect production, entrepreneurship, which increases a person's ability to work. This is also considered another unique skill set.

The set of transversal skills can vary from one field of activity to another. For example, for a teacher, his knowledge in his field is his professional skills, his speech in a foreign language, his ability to use information and digital technologies are transversal skills. On the other hand, digital technology skills are seen as professional skills for information industry workers, and not as important transversal skills for teachers. In addition, transversal skills are widely used in the education system, that is, they are considered skills of the 21st century.

They develop the skills of critical thinking, leadership, use of information and digital media, problem solving and teamwork. These skills are considered the basis of personal development and are an important part of the formation of any knowledge and skills [6].

Transversal skills are a set of skills that easily adapt to another field, are widely used in a particular field, and develop rapidly. These skills are necessary for people to function effectively not only during their studies or activities, but also in everyday life. These skills differ in that they play a key role in achieving success in any labor market.

Below are the components of cross-competence:

Transversal competence, in addition to the aforementioned skills, includes analytical skills, social and civic skills, leadership and entrepreneurial skills, as well as global citizenship. According to UNESCO, these competencies relate not only to skills, but also to values and knowledge. Transversal competencies are one of the most complex competencies in cognition, recognized in society as the main path to learning. This competence plays a crucial role in meeting the requirements of the labor market, so some studies show that this competence is also called labor competence.

Summing up the above information, we can say that transversal competence is what is considered the right and effective necessary way for the future generation to achieve its goal, covering many areas of education and science in a developing society. It is noted that in the following years, special attention is paid to the development of transversal competence.

Transversal skills are one of the values that allows future professionals to become one, as well as adapt and grow together in the changing flow of a developing society.

According to the conclusions, transversal competencies are also widely known as the competencies of the XXI century, while the strategies of higher education institutions attach great importance to the formation and development of this competence. One of the problems that should be taken into account is that in higher education institutions the concepts of "transversal competence", "transversal skills" are not used literally, or because transversal competencies consist of many components, some parts are ignored.

For this reason, it can be assumed that the development of subject competencies in education is at a high level. One of the main tasks of educational institutions is the formation of professional competencies among specialists. In addition, the formation of transversal competencies is to ensure that these professionals can find the optimal solution in any situation in the future.

Conclusion

Based on the fact that teachers have developed these competencies, skills, and abilities, they should, in addition to professional training of future specialists, contribute to the training of

qualified personnel in demand in the labor market, using new pedagogical technologies in the learning process. If this is the case, it means that the appeal of the traditional education system to modern teaching methods using digital technologies will undoubtedly prepare professionals in accordance with the requirements of society.

It should be noted that many structures of transversal competence are not yet fully integrated into the training system, on the other hand, there has long been an opinion that some structures are very well developed.

Consequently, the education system and training of specialists should be built in the direction of developing creative and innovative thinking, basic and personal, professional skills, as well as training specialists capable of conquering the world labor market.

Consequently, transversal competencies are skills that are formed and developed as a result of the joint work of teachers and students in both traditional and non-traditional forms of education. Therefore, teachers should form both professional and personal, as well as transversal competencies in the preparation of future specialists.

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